

Lost in Translation: The categorization of multidimensional constructs in the human sciences

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Abstract

There are many important, informative qualities about human subjects that are inherently immeasurable. Even qualities that are measurable, such as age, are often transformed into categories for various statistical design or analysis purposes. Despite scientific evidence to the contrary, biological sex and psychosocial gender are often categorized as binary qualities and only five to eight levels represent different race and ethnicity groups in the US Census. Translating complex, multidimensional constructs into discrete statistical variables inevitably results in information loss. Understanding the nature of that information loss within the context of the human sciences will better inform policy application and serve to counter misinformation.

This paper delves into the statistical issues associated with the kind of information loss that arises from the categorization of multidimensional human qualities. Human sex is emphasized as an example where the thoughtless adaptation of traditional categorizations and variable definitions can lead to dire consequences, statistical and otherwise. This paper presents examples where misinformation due to inappropriate categorization results in misleading statistical conclusions and suggests preventative measures beginning at the data collection stage. Finally, I consider the potential impact categorical systems of measurement have on gender and sex minorities in policy and the health science applications.

Key Words: Categorical data, human subjects, measurement system, sex/gender

1. Introduction

There are many important, informative qualities about human subjects that are inherently immeasurable. Even qualities that are measurable, such as age, are often transformed into categories for various statistical design or analysis purposes. Although not often stressed in statistics training, it is important to remember that “[t]he popularity of a form of measurement has little relationship to its accuracy or relevance...” [Hamming, 2005], especially, when dealing with categorical systems of measurement (i.e. classification).

1.1 (Mis)Measurement of Categorical Variables

Our ability to measure is limited by (among other things) our personal and cultural biases, the time during which we exist and our positionality within our society at this time, and the scope of our own experiences. Human qualities like race, ethnicity, gender, and sex are commonly studied categorical variables with systems of measurement that are subject to sociocultural norms. A rather recent trend in higher education has placed greater value on weighing these factors in biomedical applications, including the study of social determinants of health. This paper proposes that further consideration is necessary at the data collection and study design stage to ensure that our categorical measurement systems are actually able to detect the qualities of interest, rather than reflect social norms and biases. I argue that mismeasurement plagues much of the statistical analyses in the human sciences, and I will use human sex as an example to explore this argument.

1.2 Statistical Guidance

Fundamental introductions to categorical data and its analysis will cover, to various extents, the process of categorical data collection. Various sampling techniques may take advantage of stratifying a population across levels of what might, in another context, be a categorical predictor variable. This discussion often leads to solving problems related to sample size estimation as an important categorical variable may partition a population into smaller, possibly sparse subgroups. There may be some mention of sampling strategies and imputation techniques to deal with missing data, a common issue when analyzing categorical data. As a topic in statistics degree programs, the analysis of categorical data may constitute a semester's long course referencing one or more classical textbooks such as *An Introduction to Categorical Data Analysis* by Alan Agresti; *Categorical Data Analysis* by Alan Agresti; or *Analyzing Categorical Data* by Jeffrey Simonoff. Within lessons of various categorical data analysis methods such as logistic regression and inference for contingency tables, readers will find mention of Simpson's Paradox and even cautions against the concept of data dredging. Beyond the scope of these texts, advanced statistical learners may encounter measurement error models, including misclassification models. Throughout these courses, it is generally (if not always) assumed that the levels of the categorical variables under analysis are set beforehand. As AI and machine learning techniques become increasingly pervasive topics for statisticians to address, newer statistical publications may touch upon the re-use and storage of human data (c.f. e.g., Snoke and Bowen (2020)), and topics such as classification and cluster detection and analysis are increasingly prevalent in statistical journals (e.g. Amiri, Bertrand, and Clarke (2018) or Zhang, Wang, and Qiao (2018)). However, the validity of a categorical measurement system is too frequently accepted without question despite common statistical training which teaches how "the way you choose to measure things controls to a large extent what happens [in your analysis]" [Hamming, 2005].

Indeed, it is incredibly rare to find a formal statistical discussion about the mismeasurement of categorical variables. Comparably scarce is caution for statistical practitioners' responsibility to ensure they are working with a coherent measurement scale when analyzing or collecting categorical data. The pervasive view among statistical educators and researchers seems to be that responsible categorical variable definition belongs entirely within the realm of domain-specific knowledge. However, because the results of an analysis are as dependent upon a particular measurement system as they are upon the methodological approach used, I propose that more statistical guidance is necessary for the development of informative categorical data to be used in the human sciences.

1.2 Historical Context

Because we "get what we measure" [Hamming, 2005] and because our ability to measure is inherently biased for human, categorical data, it may seem curious as to why this concept is given so little formal statistical guidance. To answer the question as to why there is so little statistical consideration on the definition of categorical measurement systems, we must consider a broader historical context of this discipline. The founders of modern statistical inference, including Pearson, Galton, and Fisher, transparently conveyed their motivation to further the discipline and practice of Eugenics. The primary goal of this large academic movement was to characterize people into "superior" and "inferior" groups. Race and sex are two human qualities that were commonly referenced in (and indeed shaped by) these endeavors. As the design of experiments developed alongside tests for categorical data, these statisticians did not seem concerned with inherent limitations in categorical systems of measurement for human qualities, presumably because of their own biased motives and perspectives which asserted a "natural" ordering of human beings. One of many unfortunate consequences of this lack of critical perspective is a fundamental topic that has been largely left unexplored by the discipline; that is, the measurement (and mismeasurement) of qualitative information through categorization.

2. Education as an example

2.1 Measuring Education

Before we delve into the notion of sex as a categorical variable, let us consider the simpler human quality of education. Agresti (2013) presents this example in the first chapter of *Categorical Data Analysis* in one of the rare statistical discussions on the subjectivity of categorical variables. Agresti presents the following ways in which one may choose to measure education:

1. Is an individual receiving any formal education (yes/no)? (Binary)
2. What type of education is an individual receiving (public, private, home)? (Nominal)
3. What is the highest level of education an individual has received (e.g. highest degree attained)? (Ordinal)
4. How many years of education has an individual completed? (Interval/ratio)

This example serves to introduce readers to the different types of categorical variables which can be analyzed with type-specific statistical methods. While all four questions above measure something about an individual's educational experience, they are designed to distinguish among various aspects of education and are not interchangeable. Indeed, which (if any) of these questions to use to measure education is entirely context specific.

2.2 The Inevitability of Information Loss

As the previous example makes plain, categorical variable definition is, by nature, an *ad hoc* endeavor. This makes attempts to derive general rules for constructing such measurement systems challenging as the key component in application is critical thinking. Nonetheless, a rather general principle (to be further explored in the next section) is to move away from connotative categorizations in favor of explicitly defined levels. Furthermore, the following set of questions can serve to guide the quantitative analysis in a way that is both transparent about measurement limitations and communicates details that are necessary for reproducible research:

1. What are the similar characteristics one expects individuals in each level to share? Can these characteristics change with time?
2. How is the information necessary to classify individuals obtained?
3. Who will be missed with this classification scheme?
4. Who might be miscategorized with this classification scheme?

Although it may not be appropriate for a statistician to choose which measurement system is used in any application, statisticians are well-positioned to present such questions for domain experts to consider. These simple questions may not have simple answers, but they orient subsequent data analysis in a way that honors ethical guidelines for statistical practice [ASA, 2022].

Consider, for example, Question 1 in the previous section. If a survey collects binary responses to the question "Are you receiving any formal education?", one may surmise that the characteristics shared by the "yes" group indicate that these individuals are enrolled in an accredited educational program, whereas those in the "no" group are not. However, group membership may change with time making it crucial to account for the duration of the data-collection process. Based on the wording of the question, it seems as if respondents self-identify their education status, but it is still important to consider whether subjects are responding to an interviewer, whether that interview is conducted in person, and what the environment in which the subject answers the question looks like (at home, in public, interviewed by a doctor, etc.). When reflecting on who might be missed or miscategorized with this binary classification scheme, it becomes important to understand the age and possibly the expected educational experience of respondents. Children and some adults may not understand what is meant by the phrase "formal education" unless it is explicitly defined. For example, if the subject is a home-schooled child, or if the subject is a post-graduate adult is enrolled in a pottery class, it is not obvious how they should respond to this question. One can similarly analyze the other three questions as systems of measurement for education and it is immediately obvious that an appropriate metric in one context, will exclude or misclassify relevant information in another context. What's more, even with careful consideration of the metric, there are always be finer details about subjects' specific educational experiences that will be missed entirely by employing a finite classification scheme to a social construct (education).

3. Human sex as an example

3.1 Measuring Sex

While there are exactly two roles by which our species reproduces, human sex is more varied and dynamic than has been acknowledged historically. The predominant measurement system for human sex is the anatomical model which identifies sex through the visual inspection of external genitalia. This model however, in addition to collapsing a myriad of factors into a binary classification scheme, is insufficient for accurately classifying human subjects into a particular reproductive role. Unfortunately, despite these glaring inconsistencies, the predominant view in western society has been that sex is a binary quality and the two levels, male and female, are almost always assumed to be clearly defined despite overwhelming evidence to the contrary. (See Figure 1, for example.)

Figure 1: Image of different types of threaded (and unthreaded) pipes from *angi.com* showing an example of the pervasiveness of the binary model for sex.

Thinking a bit deeper about this human quality, people can quickly identify further dimensions of sex (beyond anatomy) that may be of interest. The diagram in Figure 2 below shows many such sex associated traits as identified by a class of college students [Velocci, 2024].

Figure 2: “Diagram of student-provided responses to the question, ‘What is sex?’” from Velocci 2024 (Figure 1).

As with the education example, one can devise various categorical variables that all measure human sex, albeit in unique ways. For example,

1. Does an individual have a prostate? (yes/no) (Binary)
2. Which gonads are functional? (testes/ovaries/neither) (Nominal)
3. Which stage of sexual development is the individual currently in? (pre-pubescent/in puberty/post-puberty) (Ordinal)
4. What is the prevalence of androgens? (there are various common ranges) (Interval/ratio)

Recently, there have been many notable attempts to improve the accuracy of quantitative research in the human sciences with respect to sex. For example, the National Institutes of Health (NIH) require the study of “both sexes” for any NIH-funded research in an attempt to address male-centric bias that has historically dominated biomedical research [NIH, 2015]. But as Smiley *et al.* (2024) point out, “while the NIH initiative Sex as a Biological Variable... sought to remedy such systemic practices, it has not addressed the underlying fundamental issue of considering sex only as a binary variable” [Smiley *et al.* 2024].

The prevalent western conceptualization of sex “reduces all sex variable biology... to asymmetric gamete production... [privileging] successful fertilization as a measure of fitness” [Smiley *et al.* 2024]. Most current and almost all previous research in the human sciences treat sex in a manner that is “overly deterministic in that it assumes anisogamy is ultimately causal for variation and diversity in sex biology” [Smiley *et al.* 2024]. Velocci (2024) also points out that the concept of sex as a biological variable and as a colloquial term is an incoherent concept yielding a dangerous “lack of specificity and rampant imprecision” within scientific research [Velocci 2024]. This historical investigation into the history of sex reveals conflicting, coexisting definitions of sex and presents evidence suggesting the use of sex as a categorical variable may be “more useful for maintaining social hierarchies [rather] than for generating scientific knowledge” [Velocci 2024]. The gist of the issue is that “operationalizing sex as a univariate, binary, categorical variable is insufficient to reveal the biology of sex” [Smiley *et al.* 2024].

Schein *et al.* (2022) remark that “[m]easures historically used to capture sex and gender typically lack validity and reliability”. For example, face-to-face or telephone surveys often entail assumption of sex of the respondent by the interviewer. “Even when ‘sex’ is assessed by a spoken question or on a self-completed form, it is usually in a format such as: ‘Are you male or female?’” making it difficult, if not impossible, to know whether respondents are reporting their assigned sex, their gender, or both [Schein *et al.* 2022]. Thus, data used as measures of both sex and gender identity may instead actually measure the interviewer’s perception of the respondent’s gender identity [Conron *et al.* 2013]. Clearly, science points to the need for an even more careful consideration than simply addressing the question “Are women included in the data?”. Fundamental statistical knowledge helps us understand why we must be careful in our treatment of this categorical variable.

3.2 The Inevitability of Information Loss and the Impact on Gender and Sex Minorities

While the information loss in the earlier example of education as a categorical variable is simple enough to imagine, I will devote more space to illustrate the prevalence and seriousness of information loss from typical measurements of sex as this is likely a less familiar concept to many readers, and it is certainly a more complex concept than measuring education.

Among the more obvious examples of information lost by reliance upon an ill-defined binary measure of sex is the exclusion or miscategorization of intersex people, that is, people with differences in their sexual development. “It is now widely acknowledged... [how the] history of medical mistreatment of intersex people, including approaches to medical management aiming for the maintenance of a strict sex binary, has caused serious harm” [Maldonado *et al.* 2024]. Indeed

the “pathologization of ambiguous genitalia” has a long history dating back to the late 1800s [Velocci 2024]. It is no coincidence that a modern academic acknowledgement of mistreatment coincides with a cultural shift to appreciate and understand variations in sex and gender.

Another group of individuals routinely missed or misclassified in the binary model for sex are transgender individuals (i.e. individuals whose sex assigned at birth does not match their gender identity). In fact, data on trans populations are not routinely collected in public health surveillance outside of HIV/AIDS research [Scheim et al. 2022]. “Perhaps the most common reason that research and data systems do not include questions or data fields for identifying trans people is that data collectors overlook the relevance of knowing who is trans” [Scheim *et al.* 2022]. Summarily, the enduring imprecision and lack of specificity of our use of sex in scientific research “fuels ongoing arguments about the purportedly biological reasons that transgender (and especially nonbinary) people are not deserving of rights or do not even exist” [Velocci 2024]. “[A] broader cultural idea of ‘biological sex’ as binary, imagined to be backed by science, is routinely deployed to exclude trans and intersex people and indeed anyone with bodily characteristics that do not fit neatly into male and female norms” [Velocci 2024].

The mismeasurement of the categorical variable sex results in missingness, marginalization, and misinformation not only for sex and gender minorities, but also fails to capture the nuances of typical sexual development. The unscientific insistence on maintaining a binary understanding of a multifaceted concept, even while multiple conflicting models of sex have coexisted, has served to justify sexist and racist social norms [Velocci 2024, Maldonado *et al.* 2024]. Academic pre-occupation with sex as it relates to reproductive capacities and “eugenic judgments about the reproductive fitness of particular people and groups” has ultimately provided authoritative support for the dehumanization of people deemed unfit to reproduce [Maldonado *et al.* 2024]. Furthermore, the sex exclusive and obsessive view of medical research has led to the exclusion of considerations of other dimensions of gender “despite growing bodies of research that highlight their importance as health determinants” [Conron *et al.* 2013].

Bioelectrical impedance analysis, employed by wearable fitness devices, is an example where the output depends on regression equations that require a binary sex/gender as their input [Albert and Delano 2021]. As is true of the vast majority of scientific research, the unmarked users such devices are designed for are White, cisgender, non-disabled men. This means that the role of the sex/gender variable (among others) is obscured when considering any individual who does not belong to this specific group. For broadly useful devices, it is necessary to “design equations that work for populations historically not included in the populations used to generate the equations. This includes non-White people, trans and nonbinary people, intersex people, people with chronic illnesses, and those at the intersections of these categories” [Albert and Delano, 2021].

Better quality data with respect to sex will improve our ability to assess health-related interventions for everyone. “Beyond assigned sex and gender identity, additional variables are often needed to characterize health-relevant dimensions of sex and gender, including hormonal milieu, genital and reproductive organs, and gender expression. Collection of these variables is needed to improve understanding of both transgender and cisgender health” [Scheim *et al.* 2022]. Conron *et al.* (2013) surmise that “[i]ncluding accurate measures of assigned sex at birth and several dimensions of gender in the health surveillance system will further our understanding of determinants of gender disparities in health and enable strategic responses to address them”.

Unfortunately, in addition to relying upon inadequate data, the current landscape of sex-difference research is riddled with erroneous statistical analyses. In their review of sex differences research, Garcia-Sifuentes and Maney (2021) found that a “substantial proportion of claimed sex differences, particularly sex-specific effects of experimental manipulations, are not supported by sufficient statistical evidence.” Regarding mandates such as that by the NIH on the treatment of sex as a biological variable, Garcia-Sifuentes and Maney (2021) astutely observe that such requirements “...may have the undesired effect of reducing, rather than enhancing, rigor and reproducibility.” Springer, Stellman, and Jordan-Young (2012) “...believe that a dedication to rectifying

longstanding male biases in medicine motivates many who currently pursue sex-difference analyses.” But they caution that “[an] overarching commitment to identifying and prioritizing difference over similarity, the prioritization of biology, the mandate to address sex as a grouping variable in federal funded research and clinical trials, regardless of biological evidence, and the mistaken belief that biology can be operationally separated from the social environment will not lead to the desired aim” [Springer, Stellman, and Jordan-Young, 2012]. I propose that the desired aim is better achieved through a more rigorous treatment of common categorical variables such as sex.

3.3 How should we measure sex?

While thoughtful consideration of the relevance of any variable is crucial for good statistical modeling, I do not suggest that sex is an irrelevant variable. In fact, failure to collect certain demographic data can prevent our ability to detect discrimination [Williams *et al.* 2018]. “...[D]epending on the research question, study design and limitations, and model system, it may still be appropriate to analyze a single sex-associated variable with two levels... for example, if sex is explicitly defined as gonadal sex and all experimental subjects have either ovaries or testes” [Smiley *et al.* 2024]. Likewise, another hasty response to the question of how we should measure sex is to declare that there should be three (or more) levels for sex. However, this answer is too hasty and fails to recognize that the automatic adaptation of categories such as “male”, “female”, and “other” can continue to perpetuate the misinformation prevalent in existing data on human sex, especially if these levels are not clearly defined within the scope of application. It may also be the case that sex information about humans is misleading without simultaneous consideration of gender. Springer, Stellman, and Jordan-Young (2012) make that case that sex is one of many “complex phenomena that are simultaneously biological and social”. Using cardiovascular disease as an example, the authors argue that “social causes should be assumed and a preponderance of evidence required before arguing for a primarily biological, non-social mechanism”.

Instead, the answer to the question of how we should measure sex is one for which there is no shortcut, that is, it requires critical thinking about the concept being measured. This is both a domain knowledge issue and a statistical issue. The statistical practitioner should be able to answer the questions presented in Section 2.2 for any categorical variable used in the analysis, including sex. In order to fully address these four critical questions, it may be the case that the binary classification scheme based on the anatomical model of human sex is insufficient in applications where it has heretofore been assumed necessary. Relying upon the typical binary model for sex, may misclassify or exclude individuals with differences in sexual development (such as those with Klinefelter’s syndrome, individuals with ovotestis or hypogonadism) or people who have undergone gender confirmation surgery. Whether or not these miscategorizations or missing data are important will depend on the study context and which specific questions the statistical analysis is designed to answer. However, in any quality application, practitioners acknowledge the known or suspected limitations of their analyses. This is challenging to do if one does not have personal experience or specialized knowledge that challenges the *status quo*; indeed, scientists are conditioned to ignore anomalies that do not fit into the schema that sex is a binary, biological truth [Velocci 2024].

Scheim *et al.* (2022) recommend (among other things) the use of enrollment and other forms that are inclusive of diverse identities and family structures and the adaptation of quality assessment tools and other metrics that incorporate the needs and experiences of trans people as “collecting gender identity data in health care settings is... critical for understanding and effectively addressing health disparities...” [Scheim *et al.* 2022]. Furthermore, “[t]rans-inclusive nondiscrimination protections are also critical to ensure that [transgender] people are protected from harm when disclosing information related to their identity or experience” [Scheim *et al.* 2022].

Another suggestion notes that “...in the vast majority of health research, ‘sex’ and ‘gender’ are entangled and analyses should proceed by assuming that measures of sex are not pristine, but include effects of gender” [Springer, Stellman, and Jordan-Young, 2012]. Among other things, Albert and Delano (2021) recommend that medical research measures physiological parameters such as

hormone levels directly, rather than assuming them based on gender or sex. The authors explicitly recommend that biomedical research in general 1) “acknowledge the existence of non-gender normative people”, 2) “make fewer assumptions”, and 3) “explain in more detail the limitations of the technology and methodology”. Similar recommendations to these are presented in Thornton *et al.* (2022). These recommendations are aligned with the American Statistical Association’s Guidelines for Ethical Statistical Practice [ASA, 2022].

There is no easy answer to the question of how to measure human sex. “[S]imply adding female cells, animals, or participants to experiments does not guarantee an improved understanding of this field of research. Rather, the experiments must also be correctly designed and analyzed appropriately...” [Vorland, 2021]. This is a job for a statistician.

4. Conclusion

Although most of this paper considers the measurement of human sex, the issues this example raises apply more broadly to other common categorical information such as gender, race, ethnicity, and more. The categorization of multidimensional constructs in the human sciences is a quality control issue of urgent importance. Amidst rapidly increasing dependence on algorithmic guidance and decision making, it is crucial that we also foster an appreciation for the limits of quantification. Because data-driven decisions can only ever be as good as the data driving them, it is important that statisticians acknowledge and contemplate the extent of information loss due to the categorization of human qualities. Only by first recognizing this issue, can we triage the severity of the information loss and provide guidance on more valid, reproducible statistical methods. Primarily, this means utilizing explicitly descriptive categorizations and avoiding connotative ones.

The intricacies of categorizing human qualities such as sex and gender present some interesting research questions for novel statistical approaches regarding categorical data. Statistical challenges include developing new methods to mitigate information loss, for example by allowing for time-dependent categorical values. Perhaps new research can produce approaches for treating qualitative information as a continuum, rather than discretized levels or can develop models with fuzzy classification schemes (e.g. Jodoin 2006). The expansion of measures of variation for categorical data is another area that should play a major role in the future of statistical education and application.

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